

Chemical Examination of *Croton sparsiflorous*

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The colouring matters extracted from *Croton sparsiflorous* have been studied. The colouring matter 'A' is an amorphous, reddish-brown solid, m.p. 133-35°. The empirical formula from analysis and mol. wt. determination of its acetyl derivative is given $C_{32}H_{34}O_{13}$. It possesses 3 OMe groups and furnishes a hepta-acetyl and an octabenzoyl derivative having a free carboxyl group, indicating that the product has a lactone ring and seven free OH groups.

The plant, *Croton sparsiflorous* (Family *Euphorbiaceae*), is a species introduced in India from South America, but has become a widely distributed plant, specially in South India.

The plant and the seeds are reported to be rich in potash. The oil from the seeds has been chemically examined¹ and found to be rich in linolic acid. Chemical examination of the plant revealed the presence of a mixture of white substances, a mixture of colouring matters, free acids, and reducing sugars.

On complete incineration, the powdered plant material left an ash content of 10.93%, of which 16.11% was water-soluble. Qualitative analysis of the ash showed that it contained calcium, magnesium, sodium, potassium, carbonate, sulphate, and silicate.

Rectified spirit was found to be most suitable from a study of the extracts of the powdered plant with different solvents. Several products were separated from the ethanolic extract. The diagrammatic scheme of the separation of these constituents is shown in Chart I.

The present communication reports the studies on one of the colouring matters, provisionally named 'Colouring matter A' of *C. sparsiflorous*.

Colouring matter 'A' is amorphous and reddish brown in colour, m.p. 133-35°. It dissolves in ethanol, methanol, acetone, chloroform, and ethyl acetate but is insoluble in ether, petroleum ether, benzene, and carbon tetrachloride. It dissolves in caustic soda and caustic potash solutions and in ammonia with a red-brown coloration; it can be precipitated on acidifying the solutions. It dissolves in sulphuric acid (conc.) with a brown coloration and is precipitated on dilution.

The empirical formula of the colouring matter 'A' was found to be $C_{32}H_{34}O_{13}$. Attempts to determine its molecular weight by ebullioscopic, cryoscopic, and Rast's method failed as the compound was neither soluble in molten camphor nor any suitable solvent could be obtained for ebullioscopic and cryoscopic determinations. Its molecular weight was, however, calculated indirectly from its acetyl derivative, which was soluble in molten camphor. It was 626, suggesting the molecular formula of the colouring matter as $C_{32}H_{34}O_{13}$.

CHART I

Hot alcoholic extract.
On cooling, a white substance deposited.

The colouring matter 'A' decolorises KMnO_4 and bromine water. It dissolves sparingly in HCl (conc.) with a deep yellow-red colour, suggesting the formation of some oxonium type of compound. It remains unchanged on boiling with $2N\text{-HCl}$ for two hours.

The compound possesses three methoxy groups, affords a hepta-acetyl derivative on acetylation, and an octabenzoyl derivative having a free carboxyl group on benzoylation. It may therefore be concluded that the compound has a lactone ring and seven free hydroxyl groups. Colouring matter 'A' does not give an oxime or a 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. On bromination in chloroform, it gave a compound having four bromine atoms in its molecule. The brominated product was oxidised with alkaline potassium

permanganate and from the reaction mixture, salicylic acid, 2,6-dibromoisovanillic acid, and oxalic acid separated. A fourth acidic compound was obtained in a very small quantity. The analysis of the dibromo-acid suggests that at least two bromine atoms have been substituted in the molecule.

On oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate, the compound 'A' gave isovanillic acid, 2-hydroxyisophthalic acid, oxalic acid, and an unidentified acidic compound. Oxidation with nitric acid furnished 2-hydroxy-5-nitrohomoisophthalic acid and mucic acid. Fusion with caustic potash gave 2-hydroxyisophthalic acid.

On methylation with dimethyl sulphate and NaOH, it furnished a compound, $C_{40}H_{32}O_{14}$. It bears eleven methoxy groups and one free carboxyl group in its molecule. This supports the presence of a lactone ring in the product 'A'. The methylated product on oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate furnished two acids, identified as salicylic acid and 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzoic acid.

On degradation with 4*N* ethanolic KOH, the compound 'A' gave a compound (B), $C_{17}H_{18}O_5$, which formed a monophenylhydrazone and a mono-oxime, showing the presence of one carbonyl group. On acetylation it formed a triacetyl derivative. It gave a violet coloration with *m*-dinitrobenzene and alkali, indicating the presence of -CO-CHOH-group in its molecule. It possesses one methoxy group. Oxidation with potassium permanganate under mild conditions gave two acids, isovanillic acid and β -(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)propionic acid. The latter was identified by its degradation into salicylic acid. Compound (B) can therefore have one of the following structures:

These may arise from compounds having the following structures respectively:

Colouring matter 'A' does not possess a carbonyl group, which eliminates the possibility of its structure as (IIb). It is, however, highly probable that compound 'B' might have structure (Ia).

The formation of 2-hydroxyisophthalic acid, obtained from the colouring matter by oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate and also by fusion with caustic potash and the formation of 2-hydroxy-5-nitrohomoisophthalic acid, the nitric acid oxidation product of the colouring matter along with the foregoing results suggest structure (III) for colouring matter 'A'.

The $-C_{13}H_{19}O_9$ moiety, which is attached to C_3 (III), should possess two methoxy groups, five hydroxy groups, a lactone ring, and a carbon chain of six carbon atoms capable of forming mucic acid on oxidation with nitric acid. Obviously, the latter indicates presence of a benzene ring in it.

Further elucidation of the structure of $-C_{13}H_{19}O_9$ moiety is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Extraction and Isolation of Colouring Matter 'A'

The plant material (80 kg.) was finely powdered and exhaustively extracted with rectified spirit. On cooling the extract, a white substance separated which was removed (yield 0.002%).

The filtrate, containing a large amount of chlorophyll, was concentrated and sufficient water and some dilute hydrochloric acid were added. This precipitated a large amount of chlorophyll. The filtrate was concentrated to remove the remaining ethanol. On cooling, the crude mixture of colouring matters with some adhering chlorophyll was precipitated and separated. The filtrate after separating the crude colouring matter was further concentrated to provide a further yield of the colouring matter.

The colouring matters were dissolved in a dilute solution of NaOH and the insoluble substances were filtered. From the solution, the mixture of colouring matters was precipitated on acidification. It was Soxhleted with ethanol, the solution concentrated to a minimum volume, and a large excess of ether was added when a precipitate appeared. It was filtered. The filtrate contained only the chlorophyll. The precipitate was redissolved in minimum quantity of acetone and reprecipitated with an excess of ether. On repeating the process, the mixture of colouring matters was completely freed of the adhering chlorophyll and waxy matters. It was reddish brown in colour.

The reddish brown mass was Soxhleted with chloroform and the chloroform solution was diluted with an excess of ether. The precipitate, thus obtained, was filtered. On recrystallisation from absolute ethanol, it melted at 133-35°. It was provisionally named colouring matter 'A'; yield 0.04%.

The residue, left after chloroform-extraction, was dissolved in minimum quantity of absolute ethanol and diluted with a large amount of chloroform when a reddish brown precipitate was obtained. It was filtered and recrystallised from methanol when a colouring matter, melting at 210-12°, was obtained. It was provisionally named colouring matter 'B'; yield 0.027%.

Colouring Matter 'A'.—It dissolves in sodium and potassium hydroxides and in ammonia, from which it can be reprecipitated on acidification. It dissolves sparingly in HCl (conc.) with a deep yellow-red coloration. It is not acidic in character. It does not reduce Fehling's solution or Tollen's reagent and does not react with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine reagent. It decolorises a solution of potassium permanganate and bromine water. (Found: C, 61.18; H, 5.61; OMe, 4.78; M. W., 626. $C_{32}H_{34}O_3$ requires C, 61.34; H, 5.43; 3OMe, 4.95%; M. W., 626).

Acetylation.—The colouring matter 'A' (1 g.) was acetylated with acetyl chloride in pyridine in the usual manner. It is brown in colour and melts at 120-21°. (Found: C, 59.87; H, 5.40; -O.CO.CH₃, 45.02; M. W., 904 (by Rast). $C_{46}H_{48}O_8$ requires C, 59.99; H, 5.22; 7-O.CO.CH₃, 44.89%; M. W., 920).

Benzoylation.—The compound 'A' (1 g.) was benzoylated with benzoyl chloride in NaOH in the usual manner and was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 148-50°. (Found: C, 71.36; H, 4.68. $C_{88}H_{68}O_{22}$ requires C, 71.55; H, 4.61%). The benzoylated product is acidic in character. [Found: Neut. equiv., 1482.3. Calc. for one carboxyl group: Neut. equiv., 1476].

Benzoylation of the Acetylated Product.—The acetylated product (0.4 g.) was benzoylated in the usual manner and recrystallised from absolute ethanol. [Found: C, 60.87; H, 5.26; M. W., 1031 (by Rast). $C_{53}H_{54}O_{22}$ requires C, 61.03; H, 5.18%; M. W., 1042]. The compound is acidic in character. [Found; Neut. equiv., 1060. Calc. for one carboxyl group: neut. equiv., 1042].

Deacetylation of the Acetylated and Debenzoylation of the Benzoylated Products.—The acetylated colouring matter (0.2 g.) was deacetylated with 0.25N-EtOH-KOH in the usual manner. The product was recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether, m.p. 133-35°.

The benzoyl derivative (0.2 g.) was similarly debenzoylated and the product was recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether mixture, m.p. 133-35°.

The melting points of the colouring matter, deacetylated product, and the debenzoylated product were not depressed when these were mixed, hence proving their identity.

Bromination.—The colouring matter 'A' (4g.) was brominated in CHCl_3 with evolution of HBr fumes. The product is insoluble in CHCl_3 . It was recrystallised from absolute ethanol as a yellowish brown solid, and not melting sharply. (Found: C, 40.58; H, 3.35; Br, 33.8. $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_{13}\text{Br}_4$ requires C, 40.67; H, 3.39; Br, 33.91%.)

Oxidation of Brominated 'A'.—The compound (4 g.) was oxidised with alkaline potassium permanganate as usual. From the reaction mixture, three acids, 'a', 'b', and 'c' were isolated.

Acid 'a', m.p. 156° , was identified as salicylic acid through its mixed melting point with a pure sample of salicylic acid.

Acid 'b' contained bromine. [Found: C, 29.34; H, 2.02; Br, 48.8; OMe, 9.65; M. W., 320. Calc. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{O}_4\text{Br}_2$: C, 29.45; H, 1.84; Br, 49.08; 1-OMe, 9.51%; M. W., 320]. It was identified as 2,6-dibromoisovanillic acid.

Acid 'c', m.p. 100° , amide m.p. 398° , was identified as oxalic acid.

Oxidation of Colouring Matter 'A'

With Alkaline KMnO_4 .—The colouring matter 'A' (6 g.) was oxidised in the usual manner. Three acids, 'd', 'e', and 'f', were isolated from the reaction mixture.

Acid 'd', m.p. $356-57^\circ$, did not depress the melting point of a pure sample of isovanillic acid. (Found: C, 56.98; H, 4.81; OMe, 18.1; M. W., 164. Calc. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{O}_4$: C, 57.14; H, 4.76; OMe, 18.45%; M. W., 168].

Acid 'e', m.p. $238-39^\circ$. It gave negative fluorescence test. Its acetyl derivative melted at $162-63^\circ$. The acid was identified as 2-hydroxyisophthalic acid. [Found: C, 52.64; H, 3.42; M. W., 187; equiv., 105. Calc. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{O}_5$: C, 52.75; H, 3.30%; M. W., 182; equiv. (dibasic), 91].

Acid 'f', m.p. 100° , was identified as oxalic acid.

A fourth acidic compound, obtained in a very small yield, could not be characterised.

With HNO_3 .—The product (4 g.) was oxidised with HNO_3 (conc.) as usual. Two acids, 'g' and 'h', were isolated from the reaction mixture.

Acid 'g', yellow in colour, contained nitrogen in the form of nitro group. It develops a green colour with ethanolic ferric chloride. [Found: C, 44.68; H, 3.1; N, 6.02; M. W., 237; equiv., 119. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_7\text{N}$ requires C, 44.81; H, 2.91; N, 5.81%; M. W., 241; equiv. (dibasic), 120.5].

The acid 'g' (0.12g.) was oxidised with alkaline potassium permanganate. An acid, m.p. $212-13^\circ$, was obtained. [Found: C, 42.15; H, 2.26; N, 5.99; M. W. (by Rast), 230. Calc. for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{O}_7\text{N}$: C, 42.30; H, 2.20; N, 6.17%; M. W., 227]. It was identified as 2-hydroxy-5-nitroisophthalic acid by mixed melting point determination with an authentic sample of the known acid. Acid 'g' is therefore 2-hydroxy-5-nitrohomoisophthalic acid.

Acid 'h', m.p. 255°, is white in colour and insoluble in ethanol. [Found: C, 34.18; H, 4.88; M. W., 201; equiv., 107. Calc. for $C_6H_{10}O_6$: C, 34.29; H, 4.76%; M. W., 210; equiv. (dibasic), 105]. Its acetyl derivative melted at 242-43°. It was identified as mucic acid.

Caustic Potash Fusion of the Colouring Matter 'A'.—The compound 'A' (3 g.) was added to fused KOH (15 g.) in a nickel crucible. The mass was heated for about 15 mins. at 300-10°. After cooling, it was dissolved in water and acidified. On concentrating the solution, a white mass separated, which on purification melted at 238-39°. It was identified as 2-hydroxyisophthalic acid.

Methylation of the Colouring Matter 'A'.—The product 'A' (4 g.) was dissolved in just sufficient volume of a dilute NaOH solution at 50-60°. Dimethyl sulphate (20 ml) and 0.5N-NaOH solution were added gradually with good stirring from separate dropping funnels over a period of one hour at such a rate that the solution always remained slightly alkaline. The mixture was then heated at 100° for half an hour to destroy the excess of dimethyl sulphate. On acidification the methylated product was precipitated. On recrystallisation from chloroform-ethanol mixture, it melted at 97-98°. It is acidic in character. [Found: OMe, 44.72; M. W., 745; equiv., 747. $C_{40}H_{32}O_{14}$ requires 11 OMe, 45.10%; M. W., 756; equiv. (monobasic), 756].

Oxidation of the Methylated Product.—The methylated product of 'A', was oxidised with alkaline potassium permanganate as usual and from the reaction mixture, two acids, 'l' and 'm', were separated.

Acid 'l', m.p. 156°, was identified as salicylic acid.

Acid 'm', m. p. 169-70°, does not possess phenolic groups. [Found: C, 56.56; H, 5.80; M. W., 208. Calc. for $C_{10}H_{14}O_5$: C, 56.60; H, 5.66%; M. W., 212]. It was identified as 3, 4, 5-trimethoxybenzoic acid.

A syrupy substance was also obtained among the oxidation products, but could not be purified further.

Degradation of the Colouring Matter 'A' with 4N-EtOH-KOH.—The compound 'A' (3 g.) was refluxed for 4 hours with 4N-EtOH-KOH. On cooling, a small amount of a white substance separated. It was filtered, dissolved in water, and the solution acidified. From this solution, a white acidic compound was obtained in a very small yield. It could not be identified.

The mother liquor was acidified and evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The residue was extracted with absolute ethanol. The solvent was evaporated and the residue was recrystallised. The pure substance melted at 280-81° and was provisionally named compound 'B'.

Compound 'B' is soluble in methanol, ethanol, and acetone. It dissolves in alkalis and ammonia. It is not acidic to litmus or sodium bicarbonate. It develops a blue-black colour with ethanolic ferric chloride and reacts with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine reagent and develops a violet colour with *m*-dinitrobenzene and alkali. [Found: C, 67.38; H, 6.04; OMe, 10.32; M. W., 315. $C_{17}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 67.54; H, 5.96; 1 OMe, 10.27%; M. W., 302].

Acetylation of Compound 'B'.—The compound 'B' (0.2g.) was acetylated with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate in the usual manner. The product was recrystallised from ethanol-ether mixture. (Found: $-O.CO.Me$, 41.17. $C_{23}H_{24}O_8$ requires $3-O.CO.Me$, 41.36%).

Phenylhydrazone of 'B'.—The compound 'B' (0.1 g.) was taken in ethanol and to it was added sufficient phenylhydrazine hydrochloride. The mixture was heated on a water bath for 3 to 4 hours. On cooling, phenylhydrazone separated. It was filtered and recrystallised from hot ethanol. [Found: N, 7.28. $C_{17}H_{18}O_4$ ($N.NH.C_6H_5$) requires N, 7.15%].

Oxidation of Compound 'B'.—The compound 'B' (1g.) was oxidised with alkaline potassium permanganate at the temperature of ice bath. From the reaction mixture, two acids, 'j' and 'k', were isolated.

Acid 'j' melted at 256-57 and identified as isovanillic acid (*vide supra*).

Acid 'k', m.p. 82-83° [Found: C, 64.8; H, 6.25; M. W., 161. Calc. for $C_9H_{10}O_3$: C, 65.06; H, 6.02%; M. W., 166] gave a blue colour with ferric chloride. Its amide melted at 69-70°. On oxidation, the acid gave salicylic acid. It is thus proved to be β -(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)propionic acid.

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